

Isocoumarino-(3,4-4',3')coumarin

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A synthesis of isocoumarino-(3,4-4',3')coumarin is described. An attempted rational synthesis of the isocoumarino-(3,4-4',3')isocoumarin, reported by Cava *et al.*¹, from 2-methoxycarbonylbenzaldehyde has furnished biphenylide (XIX).

In this communication an extension of a synthesis of isocoumarins from 2-methoxycarbonylbenzyl cyanide (cf. Chatterjea²) is reported. Thus with methyl formate and 2-methoxycarbonylbenzyl cyanide (II), the intermediate hydroxymethylene compound (III) was obtained, which cyclised to 4-cyanoisocoumarin(V). This was hydrolysed by acids to 4-carboxyisocoumarin (VI) and decarboxylated to isocoumarin (IV) (cf. Kamal *et al.*³ and Gabriel³). Similarly, by employing diethyl oxalate, the ester (VII) was readily obtainable, which was converted to isocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (VIII) by hydrolysis, followed by decarboxylation of the 4-carboxyl group.

(I): R = CHO.
(II): R = CH₂CN.

(III)

(IV) : R = R₁ = H.
(V) : R = CN; R₁ = H.
(VI) : R = COOH; R₁ = H.
(VII) : R = CN; R₁ = COOEt.
(VIII) : R = H; R₁ = COOH.

By further extension, a synthesis of 3-phenyl-4-cyanoisocoumarin (XI) has been effected by the condensation of ethyl benzoate with 2-methoxycarbonylbenzyl cyanide (II) to afford the keto-nitrile (IX) which spontaneously cyclises to 3-phenyl-4-cyanoisocoumarin (XI) with acid. The related methoxy compound (XII), which was readily prepared by way of the keto-nitrile (X), provided a quantitative yield of isocoumarino-(3,4-4',3')coumarin (XIII) on treatment with pyridine hydrochloride. This interesting compound sublimes unchanged on heating and dissolves in sodium hydroxide solution from which it can be precipitated by acidification. With methanolic ammonia, the isocoumarin (XIII) yielded the isocarbostyryl (XIV).

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 85, 2076.

2. *This Journal*, 1953, 30, 103.

3. Kamal *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3375; Gabriel, *Chem. Ber.*, 1903, 36, 870.

(IX) : R = H.
(X) : R = OMe.

(XI) : R = H.
(XII) : R = OMe.

(XIII)

(XIV)

(XV)

(XVI)

(XVII)

It was of obvious interest to attempt the synthesis of isocoumarino-(3, 4-4', 3') isocoumarin (XVII), recently isolated as a byproduct by Cava *et al.*¹ in the synthesis of quinone (XVI) from dinitro compound (XV). When 2-methoxycarbonylbenzaldehyde (I) was subjected to benzoin condensation according to the method of Irvine², a pale yellow compound having the expected composition was isolated in poor yield and none of the benzoin (XVIII) could be obtained. The compound showed carbonyl absorption at 5.60 μ and 5.80 μ (nujol) and treatment with caustic soda solution provided a compound, $C_{18}H_{10}O_5$, which showed absorption at 3.01 μ and 5.73 μ (nujol). This on sublimation lost elements of water to give back the original compound. On these grounds the compound must be biphthalide (XIX) with which it was equated by comparison with an authentic sample. Professor Cava, who also kindly examined our sample, reported that the compound was different from isocoumarin (XVII) and identical with biphthalide (XIX). Cava *et al.*¹ report IR absorption at 5.82 μ (KBr). Our results may be attributed to a better resolution and purity of the specimen. Tetramethoxy biphthalide (XX) was similarly obtained from α -methyl opianate. It may be added that

isocoumarin (XVII) completely rearranges to biphthalyl-lactonic acid (XXI) on treatment with alkali, as in the case of biphthalide (XIX).

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Methoxycarbonylbenzyl cyanide (II) was prepared from 2-carboxybenzyl cyanide by the action of diazomethane, following the procedure of Osden, and Timmis⁵, but purified by distillation. The ester distilled at 130-33°/1.5 mm. On cooling, it crystallised in needles, m.p. 41° (lit⁵. m.p. 42°).

4-Cyanoisocoumarin (V).—A solution of 2-methoxycarbonylbenzyl cyanide (0.9 g.) and ethyl formate (10 ml) in dry ether (50 ml) was added to ice-cooled, dry, and powdered sodium methoxide (from 0.46 g. sodium) with stirring. The colour of the mixture changed immediately and a yellow solid separated. Next day, ethyl formate (5.0 ml) was added to the green gelatinous reaction mixture which was refluxed for 1 hr. The solvent was removed and the residue treated with water. The clear solution was acidified with HCl (conc.) and warmed on a water bath for 10 min. The crystalline isocoumarin was collected and recrystallised from ethanol (charcoal) in colorless needles, m.p. 156°, yield, 0.7 g. (Found: C, 64.5; H, 2.1. C₁₀H₄O₂N requires C, 64.6; H, 2.3%).

4-Carboxyisocoumarin.—4-Cyanoisocoumarin (0.3 g.) was boiled under reflux with acetic acid (5.0 ml) and HCl (5.0 ml) for 8 hr. On cooling, the crystals of 4-carboxyisocoumarin separating were collected and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol in needles, m.p. 250° (lit⁶. m.p. 250-52°).

Decarboxylation of 4-carboxyisocoumarin with copper-bronze (cf. Kamal *et al.*³ and Gabriel²) furnished the isocoumarin, m.p. of which remained undepressed with the authentic sample prepared by the method of Jhonston *et al.*⁴

3-Ethoxycarbonyl-4-cyanoisocoumarin (VII).—Sodium (0.46 g.) was added to pure and dry ethanol (8.0 ml) as rapidly as possible without any loss of material. Heat was

*All m.p.s are uncorrected.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2315.

6. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1948, 13, 482.

applied to dissolve the sodium. To the warm solution a mixture of pure and freshly distilled diethyl oxalate (3.06 g.) and 2-methoxycarbonylbenzyl cyanide (3.5 g.) was added quickly and the reaction mixture was left overnight. The mixture was then diluted with water and extracted with ether to remove any unchanged material. The aqueous layer on acidification with HCl (conc.) provided the oxalyl derivative as a light brown oil. On warming the acidified mixture on a water bath for 15 min., the isocoumarin (VII) separating was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 173°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: C, 64.7; H, 3.8. $C_{13}H_9O_4N$ requires C, 64.2; H, 3.8%).

3-Carboxyisocoumarin.—3-Ethoxycarbonyl-4-cyanoisocoumarin (0.5 g.) was heated with acetic acid (8.0 ml) and HCl (8.0 ml) for 36 hr. and left overnight in a refrigerator. 3-Carboxyisocoumarin (0.2 g.) separating was collected and crystallised from hot water in needles, m.p. 243-44° (lit.⁶ m.p. 245-46°).

3-Phenyl-4-cyanoisocoumarin (XI).—To the cooled solution of 2-methoxycarbonylbenzyl cyanide (1.8 g.) and ethyl benzoate (1.63 g.) in dry benzene (30 ml) sodium hydride (0.29 g.) was added. The mixture was refluxed gently for 12 hr., cooled, and excess of sodium hydride was decomposed first by adding a few drops of ethanol and then with water. The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with ether to remove any unchanged material. The alkaline solution on acidifying with HCl (conc.) to Congo red afforded a light brown gummy mass. This was extracted with ether and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. The ethereal layer was dried ($MgSO_4$) and evaporated to provide the isocoumarin (XI) as a gummy residue. This was crystallised from ethanol in needles and sublimed at 230°/0.5 mm; m.p. 205-206°. The isocoumarin was obtained unchanged from its alkaline solution on acidification. (Found: C, 77.0; H, 3.6. $C_{16}H_9O_2N$ requires C, 77.6; H, 3.6%).

On carrying out the condensation in presence of sodium methoxide, the isocoumarin (XI) was obtained only in traces.

3-(2'-Methoxyphenyl)-4-cyanoisocoumarin (XII).—To a cooled solution of 2-methoxycarbonylbenzyl cyanide (1.3 g.) and ethyl *o*-methoxybenzoate (1.6 g.) in dry benzene (40 ml) was added sodium hydride (0.23 g.) with stirring. When the evolution of hydrogen had ceased, the mixture was refluxed gently for 18 hr. On working up in the usual manner, a gummy mass was obtained which was taken in ether and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. The ethereal layer was dried ($MgSO_4$) and evaporated to provide a gummy residue. The substance was then warmed on a water bath with acetic acid and a few drops of HCl (conc.). On cooling, the isocoumarin (XII) obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 175-76°, yield 0.7 g. This dissolved in a 10% NaOH solution and was obtained unchanged on acidification. (Found: C, 74.0; H, 4.1. $C_{17}H_{11}O_3N$ requires C, 73.6; H, 4.0%).

Isocoumarino-(3,4-4',3')coumarin (XIII).—3-(2'-Methoxyphenyl)-4-cyanoisocoumarin (0.1 g.) was heated with pyridine hydrochloride (1.0 g.) at 210-20° for 1 hr. in CO_2 atmosphere under dry condition. First a homogeneous solution was obtained which deposited needles at that temperature. On working up in the usual manner, the coumarin (XIII) was obtained in quantitative yield. This was crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 282.5°. The compound sublimed and dissolved in warm 10% NaOH solution. The original compound was precipitated from the alkaline solution. (Found: C,

72.6; H, 3.2. $C_{16}H_8O_4$ requires C, 72.8; H, 3.1%). The compound shows carbonyl absorption at 5.72 μ and 5.89 μ .

Attempted Self-condensation of 2-Methoxycarbonylbenzyl Cyanide.—A solution of 2-methoxycarbonylbenzyl cyanide (1.75 g.) in dry benzene (25 ml) was added to cooled, dry, and powdered sodium methoxide (from 0.23 g. of sodium). On working up in the usual manner, the ester (1.5 g.) was obtained unchanged. A very small quantity of a gummy mass was obtained which could not deposit any crystal.

Action of Ethanolic Ammonia on Isocoumarino-3,4-4',3'coumarin.—The isocoumarin (20 mg.) was heated with methanolic ammonia in a sealed tube at 100° for 30 hr. The tube was opened carefully. The solvent was removed and the residue was treated with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was dried ($MgSO_4$) and evaporated to yield the isocarbotyrl (XIV). This was crystallized from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 310°. (Found: C, 73.2; H, 3.6; N, 5.4. $C_{16}H_9O_3N$ requires C, 73.0; H, 3.4; N, 5.3%).

Methyl o-phthalaldehyde was obtained from o-phthalaldehydic acid by the action of diazomethane in 76% yield.

Biphtalide (XIX).—Methyl o-phthalaldehyde (3.5 g.) was dissolved in minimum volume of ethanol (50%). The solution was treated with potassium cyanide (0.5 g.) and warmed on a water bath for 30 min. The solution turned yellow and a light yellow precipitate separated. This was cooled in ice and biphtalide was collected and crystallized either from acetic acid or xylene in pale yellow, long needles, m.p. 327° (lit. report m.p.; 327°. Ramirez *et al.*⁸ report m.p. 352-54° and Sauer *et al.*⁹, 334°). Melting point remained undepressed when mixed with an authentic sample prepared by the method of Ramirez *et al.*⁸ by heating phthalic anhydride with triethyl phosphite in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The compound shows carbonyl absorption at 5.62 μ and 5.80 μ . (nujol). (Found: C, 72.8; H, 3.3. $C_{16}H_8O_4$ requires C, 72.8; H, 3.1%).

Hydrolysis.—Biphtalide (0.2 g.) was heated on a water bath with 10% NaOH solution (10 ml). First a yellow solution was obtained which turned pink and finally light yellow. The solution was filtered and the clear solution was acidified with HCl (conc.). The hydrolysed product (XXI) was collected and crystallized from acetic acid in colorless plates, m.p. 260-61°. (Found: C, 67.8; H, 3.4. $C_{16}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 68.09; H, 3.54%).

The compound absorbs at 3.01 μ (OH group) and 5.73 μ (carbonyl group) in the IR. This on heating sublimed to provide pale yellow needles, the m.p. of which was not depressed when mixed with biphtalide.

α-Methyl opianate was prepared from opianic acid (1.5 g.) by the action of diazomethane (from 2.0 g. of nitrosomethylurea) in the usual manner. The ester distilled at 230°/50 mm (lit. 233-34°/55 mm), yield 1.2 g.

7. Graebe and Sahamalsigang, *Annalen*, 1885, 223, 134.

8. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 1838.

9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 3677. ♦

6,7-6', 7'-Tetramethoxybiphtalide (XX).— α -Methyl cplanate was dissolved in minimum quantity of ethanol (50%) and warmed on a water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. with potassium cyanide. The yellow solid of the biphtalide was collected and crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 305°. The compound shows carbonyl absorption at 5.60 (shoulder) and at 5.70 μ . (Found: C, 62.5; H, 4.4. $C_{20}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 62.5; H, 4.2%).

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Received December 14, 1964.